

experiment, using plots with and without insecticide, was used 1979-81 on four susceptible rice varieties — RD1, Leaug-Laung, Dawk-Ma-Li 105, and Niew-San-Pahtawng — in a strip plot design with three replications. In treated plots carbofuran (1 kg ai/ ha) was incorporated into the soil before planting and broadcast on paddy water 20 and 40 days after transplanting.

The second assessment method observed individual hills. Leaug-Laung was transplanted in a 0.08-ha field in 1981. Gall midge-infested tillers (silver-shoots) and total tillers were counted from 10 randomly selected rows/plot, 50 hills/row, 500 hills/ plot. Yield per hill was recorded. A wide range (0, 1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-30, 31-50, and 51-70%) of infestation levels which could be correlated with yield were obtained with this method.

Results from the conventional insecticide plot method showed potential yields varied annually, possibly because of weather factors (see table). Relating rice yield to gall midge infestations was unsuccessful because it would require many years to get a wide range of gall midge infestation levels. High gall midge infestation (average of 69% infested tillers) occurred in 1980. Yield reduction in all varieties ranged from 42 to 50%. Less damage (22-23%) occurred in 1979 and 1981. Yield loss variation was greater at lower levels of infestation. In most cases Niew-San-Pahtawng and Dawk-Ma-Li 105 showed lowest losses. Gall midge infestation induced rice tillering, and there were more tillers in untreated plots than in treated ones but panicle number was small.

Results from the single hill experiment demonstrated that tiller number increased gradually with increasing gall

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Insecticide treatment ^b	Infested tillers (%) 55-65 DT	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	1.6	8.5	6.8	3.6	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	16.2	9.3	5.5	2.8	22
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	3.7	10.8	8.1	3.2	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	21.9	12.3	7.6	2.9	10
Leaug-Laung	Treated	3.7	8.8	7.1	3.1	—
Leaug-Laung	Untreated	20.2	9.9	6.7	2.1	13

^aAv of 3 replications. Insect damage and yield components were measured from 30 random hills. DT = days after transplanting. ^b1 kg ai carbofuran/ha was incorporated into the soil before transplanting, and broadcast 20 and 40 DT, except in 1979 trial when only 2 broadcast applications (20 and 40 DT) were made.

midge infestation (see figure). The general yield loss equation was $Y = 5.118 + 0.52 X$ (when $Y = \% \text{ yield loss}$ and $X = \% \text{ silvershoots}$). When this equation was used to determine average yield loss for the four rice varieties, the results closely agreed with those of the conventional method.

Data showed average potential rice yield was 2.64 t/ha. Using the yield loss equation, yield reduction at 20% gall

midge infestation is 15.6% or 411 kg/ha, costing \$57.5 (when 1 t rice = \$140) in lost production. Two applications of carbofuran cost \$57.2 (1 kg of carbofuran = \$0.86). Therefore, treating infestation levels above 20% will give a return benefit to cover the cost of control. Because annual gall midge infestation of rice at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, is more than 20%, insecticide application is economic.. ✎

Relationships between percent gall midge infestation and number of tillers and yield loss in Leaug-Laung rice variety at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, 1981.

Leersia hexandra as weed host for the brown planthopper

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* that normally develops on *Leersia hexandra* weed has been found at two sites on the IRRI farm. Incuba-

tion period and egg hatchability were tested in 10 replications.

Five gravid females were enclosed in each 6- × 30-cm mylar cage and allowed to oviposit for 24 hours on *Leersia* plants. The insects were removed and nymphs that hatched were counted and removed daily. When hatching terminated, plants were dissected and unhatched eggs counted.

BPH longevity and fecundity were also studied. Pairs of newly emerged adults were placed on potted *Leersia* in a mylar cage. Insects that died were counted and removed daily. Living insects were transferred every 3 to 4 days to fresh host plants. Plants from which adults were removed were dissected and eggs were counted.

Incubation period was 7.8 days, egg

hatchability 81%. Males lived 27 days and females 33 days, and fecundity was 513 eggs. Data are equivalent to BPH biotype 1 data from TN1 plants.

Leersia-reared BPH fed little on rice plants, as indicated by low amounts of excreta, and did not survive on TN1 and several resistant varieties. Rice-plant-reared BPH populations, tested in the greenhouse, did not live on *Leersia*, but could contribute to the rice-feeding BPH gene pool through intermingling.

A crossing experiment was conducted to determine if *Leersia*-reared and rice-plant-reared BPH mate and to assess the virulence of the offspring. Individual fifth-instar nymphs of *Leersia*-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing *Leersia* cuttings and greenhouse rice-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing TN1 seedlings. Using adults that emerged simultaneously, crosses of

Survival of progeny from crosses between *Leersia* brown planthopper (BPH) and rice-reared BPH at 15 days after being placed on *Leersia* and TN1 plants.

Leersia BPH and rice-reared BPH were caged on *Leersia* and TN1 plants planted together in a clay pot. When eggs hatched, 10 newly emerged nymphs were caged on separate potted *Leersia* and TN1 plants. Some F₁ progenies sur-

vived (see figure) and produced F₂ progenies on *Leersia* and TN1 plants. If intermingling also occurs under field conditions, the wild *Leersia* BPH population can contribute to BPH field infestation. ✎

The flea beetle as a rice pest in Assam, India

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The flea beetle *Chaetonema basalis* Baly. was studied on rice plants during transplanting and tillering stages in ahu (March-July) and sali (July-December)

1980-81 in Assam, India. Mild infestations were reported in Barpeta Agricultural Subdivision, Kamrup, Assam, but there was no significant economic damage.

Adults are small, round, black, shining beetles about 1.5 to 2 mm long. They are found on leaves and jump when disturbed. They feed by scraping the green matter from leaves, leaving short straight lines on the leaf surface

that are parallel to leaf veins. Damage resembles that caused by the rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera*. Later, ends of affected leaves turn brown and wither. Heavily infested fields look scorched. In severely infested fields 25-40 beetles/hill can be found.

A rabi oilseed survey has shown that the pest also attacks mustard pods during winter. ✎

Rice thrips in Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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Rice thrips *thrips oryzae* Williams have become a major problem at the INA experimental farm, Mymensingh, and in adjacent areas. During 1982 aus season (summer rice) all varieties on the farm (high yielding and local) were severely damaged. In some cases infestation was 100%.

Infestation occurs in seedling and early growth stages. Thrips nymphs and adults suck sap from the leaves. In heavy infestation plants may dry.

Thrips increase might have been

caused by the long winter and summer drought and by the destruction of natural enemies through heavy insecticide application. Infestation decreased with the onset of rainy season. ✎

Status of the brown planthopper in Thailand

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Brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is one of the most destruc-

tive rice pests in central Thailand. In 1981, 36,000 ha were severely damaged. In a survey of pest status April-June 1981, BPH populations and natural enemies were estimated by direct counting (50 hills/field) and sweep net (50 sweeps/field) at 42 sites in 9 provinces, BPH eggs and egg parasites were sampled by dissecting 10 random hills at each location. BPH was in 95% of samples. Density was 204 adults and nymphs/50 hills and 6.5/50 sweeps (see table). Rice ragged stunt disease (RSV) was in 43% of sites, averaging 5% infected hills. Natural enemies — damselflies, wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, long-jawed orb weaver *Tetragnatha* spp, and coccinellid beetle *Micrapis discolor* — were abundant. Mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* population was